

Day to day management of anxiety and depression

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This is not a regurgitation of the textbooks. I think you will find that when you use homœopathic medicines your need for standard antidepressants and anxiolytics will steadily decline; this is certainly something which I have found. Here, when you think about it, are two groups of conventional medicines, the anxiolytics and antidepressants, which really have been woefully over prescribed during the last couple of decades in general practice. As a result we now have hundreds of thousands of what one might call psychotropic addicts in our land and this is because there has been a tremendous over-prescription of these ordinary drugs. I think this is a field where one can very quickly see some of the very simple advantages of homœopathic medicines. These are all pretty well known to you:—freedom from side-effects, such a big problem with the psychotropic group of drugs, and then this particular factor, —safety from the possibility of overdosage.

This is a very useful area when using homœopathic therapeutics in the acute situation in general practice because, obviously, there is always a problem, or at any rate a potential problem, of patients taking an overdose of their tablets. This has happened to me on a number of occasions where one has prescribed remedies for a patient and later the same day relatives have rung up and said: 'Horrors, Veronica has taken the whole bottle'. It is very nice to just be able to say: 'Well, that's fine and not to worry about it at all,' because you are not going to do any damage. So that is really quite an important point in being able to use homœopathic therapeutics in this particular field: and then, of course, there is an important point:

—that homœopathic medicines are free from problems of drug abuse or addiction.

I am going to review a number of medicines some of which are very major medicines, but I only want to highlight that part of their materia

medica which is pertinent to the field of anxiety and depression as encountered in general practice, and I want to indicate some of the clinical situations in which I find these medicines useful. Very largely speaking I will be talking about what I might call the neurotic or emotional rather than the psychotic end of the scale. I think treating true psychoses using homœopathic therapeutics is extremely difficult and probably not something for you to try getting involved in too quickly. I think it is also fair to say that true psychotic patients are relatively uncommon in the average practice. When you think around all the patients you have in your practice who might fall into this group of patients, where anxiety and depression might be the diagnosis, you will probably think to yourself that there is only a very small number of them who are truly psychotic.

So we are going to be looking at medicines which would be useful for the vast majority of these patients you see in the average practice. I think it goes without saying that the nearer you get to the totality of the symptoms of your patient the better suited the medicine is going to be and the better result you are going to get; but that is not always possible in an NHS general practice; we cannot set about long histories in the middle of the morning surgery. You may however recall me saying on the Introductory Course that if you've been in a practice for a while, you probably know your patient, so that you are going to be able to fill in some of the picture from your previous knowledge.

Take advantage of that and, secondly, be as observant as you possibly can be, because there are many things that you can observe and which will help you to enlarge the picture and get as close as possible to the totality. As we run through some of the medicines I do not intend to go through massive amounts of materia medica. You can look them up for yourselves. This is not an exercise in spoon-feeding. What I am trying to do is to jog your memories or give you some ideas of medicines that may be helpful and I shall

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rely on you to go away and look the medicines up: look up the repertory and see which medicines you might feel are going to be appropriate for you to use.

Anxiety

There are 37 medicines in bold type in the 'anxiety' rubric in Kent's *Repertory* and there are a further 87 medicines in italic type, let alone the number that there are in ordinary type. So there are a large number of medicines involved. Now if we stick with the repertory and look at depression, we do not actually find depression as such in the repertory. It comes under 'sadness'. You will find that the main rubric is sadness, and then in parentheses after that it says 'mental depression'. In that rubric we have got 47 remedies which are in bold type and a further 91 which are in italics. If we superimpose these two rubrics in the repertory you can see that these are the medicines—many of them you would expect to see—which actually come through.

Aconite you might expect; *Arsenicum*; *Lycopodium*. These are the ones which come through in bold type. Now there are obviously some in bold type in the sadness rubric which are not in both. *Aurum* is there, of course. All the other remedies that are in the anxiety rubric are in the depression rubric as well; all of these are in fact in italics, with the exception of *Bismuth* which does not appear at all in the depression rubric, and *Secale* which only appears in ordinary type. That covers the two main rubrics in the repertory.

Do look at the repertory—look at these particular rubrics—look at the medicines which come through strongly and consider how useful they might be to you in clinical practice. When we break it down a bit, staying with the repertory again, if you qualify anxiety, you find that the medicine lists become very much smaller.

This means that under anxiety we then start looking at situations in which the patient is anxious, e.g. during thunderstorms = *Phosphorus*. There are only bold type remedies. So you have only got one medicine coming through in bold type there, and one can, in fact, narrow it down very well. Anxiety anticipating an engagement: *Argentum nitricum* is the only bold type remedy. Notice the medicines that come through on a number of occasions—*Arsenicum* for instance comes through as a bold type remedy in quite a number of places. This immediately gives you the impression of the anxious nature of the *Arsenicum* patient. The repertory is really quite

helpful and informative if one looks through it in this way to see which medicines come out strongly in bold type in any particular group of rubrics. So do look at it and see how it will be helpful in directing you to medicines you should consider.

Let us move on now to practical clinical situations, keeping with anxiety to begin with. How do you think I felt this morning at the prospect of having to give this lecture? Terribly anxious—so you might be thinking of some medicines that are apprehensive and anxious. If we look at this rubric—'anxiety, anticipating an engagement' we have got *Argentum nit.* down there in bold type; *Gelsemium* and *Medorrhinum* are the other two remedies that are in that rubric. 'Anxiety, if a time is set' is another rubric which would be appropriate to me this morning. *Argentum nit.* in italics and again *Gelsemium* and *Medorrhinum*. There is a rubric under 'Fear; church or opera when ready to go'; *Argentum nit.* again in bold type and *Gelsemium* in italics. Then, of course, there is the rubric for anticipation, where you get these medicines coming through and again. You have got those three we have been talking about: *Argentum nit.*, *Gelsemium*, *Medorrhinum*, together with the other three: *Arsenicum*, *Lycopodium*, *Silica*.

Argentum nit. and *Gelsemium*, I suggest are the two most useful ones in every-day general practice; what one might call specifics or semi-specifics for this type of problem—for the chap who is coming up to London to give a lecture and is really very nervous and apprehensive about it. People who are worried about flying, about taking their driving tests, about forthcoming exams, all these sorts of common everyday situations that we meet in general practice. So those one might think of very much as the more 'local' medicines, as one might call them.

Arsenicum and *Lycopodium* are rather deeper-acting medicines that I tend to think of much more in a constitutional way and they are obviously very useful in the patient who you feel is close to that particular constitution. So many people ring up in general practice—the mums ring up and say: 'Georgina's got her A-levels in a fortnight and she's in a terrible state about it; or she's taking Grade VI piano or whatever, can the doctor give her anything?' There I would suggest that *Argentum nit.* and *Gelsemium* are the two medicines that you would consider top of the list.

Those two may be considered in more detail. The materia medica of *Argentum nit.*: fearful, anxious, apprehensive—those are the strong

features. Anxiety causes diarrhoea. The patient may well tell you that they have a terribly loose tummy just prior to doing something. It is very much the patient who is a little on the neurotic side. That is a frontline thing to think about. You have been through all the other general features of *Argentum nit.* already this morning, so we will skate across them.

Gelsemium has effects of fright, fear, excitement/trembling. This is a very strong feature of the patient who needs *Gelsemium*, so watch out for it, and ask for it if necessary. For stage fright, exam nerves, all the sort of situations that I have mentioned to you just now, *Gelsemium* may be extremely useful. Particularly the trembling; the patient who tells you that they get into a terrible state of the trembles with something that they have got to do—very useful for people who are taking things like piano exams—it is very difficult to play the piano when you are trembling! This, then, is the remedy to think of for the patient who is anxious before exams or anything they have got to do, where trembling is a particular feature.

Going back to our 'anticipation' rubric, we will mention in passing out old friend *Lycopodium*: sensitive, anxious, apprehensive—those are very much the mental features of *Lycopodium*. Intellectual people very often have an anticipatory fear of failure. Consider, therefore, whether the patient is a *Lycopodium* type, at any rate in a situation like this. You might use *Lycopodium* for this particular situation of apprehension about a forthcoming ordeal.

Staying with anxiety, it is obvious that the closer we get to the totality of the symptoms the better we are going to be able to help the patient. We therefore need to look for very much more detail if we are going to do something which is in the long term more helpful. We are going to do better to use one of the more major medicines or polychrests. If you are using *Argentum nit.* or *Gelsemium* as a specific—I tend to use it in the 6th potency, but you could equally well use it in the 30th potency and give it twice or three times a day. Either potency would be perfectly adequate and if you are beginning I would perhaps stick with the 30th potency. It saves you having other things to consider.

Thinking of constitutional remedies: some of these medicines are particularly anxious. *Arsenicum* is a very anxious medicine; *Lycopodium* is also a very anxious medicine; *Phosphorus* tends to be rather anxious and I think one would say *Silica* was also rather anxious. A number of the

others also have anxiety as part of their mental picture. If we were to consider three major anxiety medicines—we have already looked at *Argentum nit.* this morning—the other two would be *Arsenicum* and *Lycopodium*.

Arsenicum: think of anxious, restless, fearful, fastidious—these are the four main mental symptoms of the *Arsenicum* patient. The aggravation time is particularly important and they tend to be very chilly patients. You may well be able to cast your mind round some people in the practice and actually think of patients who are like this: rather restless, anxious people who are frightfully pernickety, fussy and tidy and have to have everything done just so. That type of patient would be very well suited by *Arsenicum* and if you can use it on a constitutional basis you will do much more long term good for the patient.

Now let us come back to *Lycopodium*. This is an extremely useful medicine, one which was originally proved by Hahnemann and a substance which, of course, had previously been thought to be totally inert. It is made from the spores of the club moss and had been used for all sorts of things—wrapping pills, etc—in the past because it was thought to be inert. It was not until Hahnemann prepared it by trituration that it was realized that the spores had medicinal properties. It is an oily substance in the spores which has medicinal properties and you need to fracture the spores in order to release it.

When we look at Hahnemann's provings we get the impression of a severely dyspeptic patient. Indigestion discolours the whole of his life; anxious and irritable, muddle and confused. Most of his troubles follow the consumption of food: the heartburn, the waterbrash, the flatulence, the rumblings, the fullness and distension, the discomfort in the rectum occur over and over again in the provings. Other mucous membranes are also affected: the nose, the conjunctivae, the pharynx and urinary tract. But with all the provings of *Lycopodium* none is more clearly determined than the profound effect on the digestion and the excessive production of wind. So these are the things that come through very strongly in the provings and in fact it is in many of the later materia medicas that one gets the mental side coming out rather more strongly. These patients tend to look older than their years. Now do not be too misled by appearance; it can be helpful, but it can also be misleading if you put too much emphasis on it; but with *Lycopodium* that can be quite a large feature. Wor-

ried frown, the anxiety—tends to be visible in the *Lycopodium* patients. They are frequently intellectual people; frequently professional people, teachers, accountants, doctors, people like that; but do not debar people from being *Lycopodium* if you just think they are not very intellectual or intelligent. It is however frequently useful in people who have a strong intellect.

They are very sensitive patients, sensitive in a very large variety of ways. Sensitive to all sorts of impulses that they get and as a result they can be rather sort of crabby and irritable. They are often very irritable with their children—especially small children; it is almost as though they are a bit above that, and they really cannot quite cope with the sort of endless nagging of little children. So they are very sensitive to all sorts of things. They are emotional people, although they do not really like to show their emotions: a little bit like *Natrum mur.* here. But they do tend to be emotional people and they will do strange things, like burst into tears when somebody is thanking them for something, and so the emotions do come out sometimes. Then they have the anxiety that I have already mentioned, apprehension about forthcoming things—a very strong feature. There is another very important feature with the *Lycopodium* patient: when they actually come to do what they have got to do they do it quite well—probably much above their own expectations. There are other medicines that also have apprehension but do not perform terribly well when they actually come to do what they have got to do. Those two things grouped together—the apprehension, and yet dealing with the problem well when it arrives—very much fit the *Lycopodium* picture.

They have this strange, almost contradictory thing of fearing to be alone yet are not keen on company. It sounds contradictory on paper but it is not really. They are not terribly keen on company and socializing; they like selected company; they like to have a dinner party with Mary and John or whatever because those are people they know and they like socializing in that way. They fear being alone particularly when they are unwell. The books say of *Lycopodium* that they fear being alone; they do not want anybody in the room with them but they would like to know somebody's in the house so that they can call them if they need to. So they have a very real fear of being alone, particularly when unwell.

You may also pick this up: making mistakes in

speech and writing. Some patients will complain of that, professional people especially; you may find them actually telling you about that particular problem. Fitting it in together with this mental picture of *Lycopodium* you will get the whole picture quite well.

The time aggravation can be very useful; you may not find it but it is a very strong feature sometimes in *Lycopodium* patients. It can be morning or evening. Much more commonly we think of it as a 4–8 p.m. time aggravation, or perhaps 4–6 p.m. dragging on till 8 p.m. and then better again after that. But you do see some *Lycopodium* patients who suffer a lot from waking up in the early morning and worrying. They are the sort of patients who are awake at 4 and 5 o'clock in the morning and worry about all the things that are going to happen in the day that lies ahead. They often go to sleep again and have great difficulty waking up when it is time to actually get up. So you see this time aggravation in the early morning.

You may well find that your *Lycopodium* patient has the main strong dyspeptic symptoms of the *Lycopodium* materia medica. You may have to dig for it, but it is always worth asking in passing. One quick question: 'What is your digestion like?' will often reveal quite a lot and might just help to cement the picture for you and make you realize that this is the right medicine to use.

This is *Lycopodium* used much more in a constitutional way. You may give the same patient, off the cuff, *Argentum nit.* or *Gelsemium* for a particular event, but if you are going to actually help them to be a good deal better, to raise their base line as it were and, therefore, their resistance to the anxiety problem, you need to treat the *Lycopodium* constitution.

Depression

I think it is worth looking at some types of emotion and thinking about the medicines that might be appropriate, because very often your depressed patient has in fact got some emotional disturbance and it may well be that the remedy that is applicable to that emotional disturbance will be the one that is best indicated.

ANGRY MEDICINES. These are the medicines to think about in a patient whose depression is really very much bound up with anger over a particular situation. Somebody asked Dr Leary earlier on about using other forms of treatment; whether we would use psychotherapy or whatever. Obviously it is of paramount importance,

dealing with this group of conditions, that one goes behind the presenting symptoms and tries to find out what is at the root of it all, because putting that right is going to be probably the most important thing. Think about *Colocynthis*, *Nux vomica*, *Chamomilla*. Those are three particularly angry medicines and may be very appropriate.

RESENTMENT. This is a very very potent cause of reactive depression in general practice. *Staphysagria* has resentment as an extremely strong feature; they tend to be very irascible patients; very angry and irritable but they have got this terrific underlying resentment about something that has happened or is happening. This may be some problem at work which they are extremely resentful about—somebody's got promotion over them when they feel they should have got it. *Staphysagria* may well be the key to unlock that depression and improve the situation. *Natrum mur.* is another medicine which has resentment very strongly in its materia medica. These patients are much less forthcoming of course—we will come back to them.

THE WEEPY PATIENT. Think of *Pulsatilla* as the first thing you might consider, although a number of other medicines may present as being weepy: *Ignatia*, which we will come back to, comes under this heading; *Sepia* can also be quite weepy. *Pulsatilla* has the very mild type of temperament which is very weepy as well. *Ignatia* is very much more the hysterical type of picture—the hysterical type of temperament which is also weepy.

THE INDIFFERENT PATIENT. *Sepia*, very indifferent; indifferent particularly to family and loved ones; as opposed to *Phosphorus*, which is really rather what I would call 'apathetic when ill'. *Phosphorus* does not tend to be indifferent at all when well. They are very effervescent and vivacious people when they are well, but they tend to get rather apathetic when they are unwell. This can particularly be seen in the depressed *Phosphorus* patient, who can have a very acute, deep, black depression and be very apathetic indeed. It may of course be very useful for you to find out from the family what they are normally like if you do not know them. But in the general practice situation you probably do know them and you may know that they are now very different to how they usually are.

SYMPATHETIC PEOPLE. *Phosphorus* and *Causticum* particularly have that as a strong feature; not terribly relevant to depression.

FRIGHT AND SHOCK are relevant. *Aconite* is

one of the medicines on our programme and is a medicine very useful in the situation of fright or shock.

SUICIDAL. We have talked about *Aurum met.* **JEALOUSY AND SUSPICION**—with *Lachesis* and *Hyoscyamus* also. We have skated over all these already.

Let us consider some of these medicines in more detail.

Aconite is purely an acute medicine. Look for this mental picture in the patient who needs *Aconite* in the acute situation, fear and terror, intense anxiety, very restless, very panic stricken. *Aconite* will be your medicine of choice there. Repeated frequently this very short-acting medicine would be very useful in that particular situation.

Ignatia is particularly useful under the heading of grief. I use it in what I call the situation of acute grief as opposed to the sub-acute or chronic, which is very much more *Natrum mur.* *Ignatia* covers the effects of shock and grief and disappointment—you will nearly always find the hysterical element in the patient who needs *Ignatia*. Very emotional people; a lot of sighing and sobbing, and can be really quite melancholy and depressed. An interesting symptom is a sensation of a lump in the throat—'globus hystericus'. *Ignatia* is very useful for that and, heaven knows, it is not easy to treat using ordinary therapeutics; that is something for which *Ignatia* can be extremely useful. *Ignatia* is much more an acute medicine. The girl who comes in: her boyfriend had just given her up and she is in floods of tears and really quite over the top about it all. *Ignatia* is very useful for that sort of situation; later on the same day she takes the whole bottle and you are quite safe. That has happened to me several times. *Ignatia* is therefore very useful in that particular acute situation: hysterical weeping, effects of shock, grief, disappointment, etc.

Natrum mur. is a much more deep-acting medicine for use in the depression that may follow grief or bereavement. These patients are not easy to get details out of. They can be weepy patients but they will only weep when they are alone; they do not like to show their emotions; they are very much people who bottle everything up; they cannot express their emotions; they do not like to anyway, because they do not like to be seen; and, of course, there is one strong feature: they cannot bear to be consoled or anybody to make a fuss or bother over them. Think of this in bereavement situations for the sub-acute or

chronic situation; ill effects of grief; depressed patients can be a little bit on the irritable side; they have this lovely phrase applied to them in some of the books: 'nice to know but awful to live with', and I think there is quite a bit of truth about that. They are very poor at mixing with other people; they like a lot of their own company and they are not good at mixing with others.

There are a lot of other features; obviously, it is a very large medicine indeed, with strong general features. They often have a salt modality. I have not put down 'desires salt', which it says in most of the books; you do occasionally meet a patient who actually does not like salt but who really is a *Natrum mur.* patient. But they often or nearly always will have a salt modality. Similarly they frequently have a seaside modality and they are nearly always worse at the seaside, but occasionally one can get the opposite. They are chilly patients—this is another of these apparently rather contradictory statements.

They tend to be chilly patients, but they are definitely worse for heat, for humid muggy heat and therefore worse in stuffy rooms. These are very strong adjuvant factors, general modalities, and yet the patients may tell you that they tend to be rather chilly. So that you see (you get that a little bit with *Pulsatilla* as well) they can be chilly patients but very much made worse for a fog and for humid heat.

Think of *Natrum mur.* as a more deep-acting remedy in your depressed patient who has suffered very much from the ill effects of grief and who has this particular mental picture. Now if we go back to the depression of sadness/mental depression rubric in the repertory, all these medicines are in fact in that rubric. So you can see how markedly emotional disturbances come through to cause, or be a very potent factor in, any of the depressive states that we see in everyday general practice, and these are some of the medicines which I think you will find extremely useful.